

Part 2 Biomechanics in endodontics (Article Series), Theoretical framework and development of computational model of dentine fatigue, Stupid models for interpreting living organs

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Abstract

Modern endodontic treatments include reinforcement of the restoration by utilizing post that extending inside the root canal. Different commercial products are present in the market that had different mechanical properties. Two main categories are present, plastic post reinforced by fibers or metallic post. The effect on the fatigue properties of the dentine had been investigated in this paper from mechanical perspective

Keywords: Teeth, Biomechanics, Dentine fatigue, Fiber post, Metallic post, Endodontic treatment.

Introduction

Fatigue is an important property of the materials. It is a mark of materials failure due to repetitive stress below the maximum stress that the material tolerate. In the engineering materials, a level of the applied stress would not cause any damage to the material whether applied intermittent or in an indefinite status is called endurance limit. This also include all stresses below (1).

In the case of the living materials, we have a fascinating remodeling mechanism. Any remodeling process needs 2 separate processes (2)

- Mechanical damage monitoring
- Stiffening mechanism

Hard tissues had 3 varieties

- Non modifiable non-remodelable
- Modifiable non-remodelable
- Modifiable non-remodelable

In the case of the hard tissues (3)

- Enamel and middle ear ossicles is belonging to the first category and this is established via different pathways and process
- Dentine is belonging to the second group where new dentine is added, but the original structure is not changed
- Bone and cartilage are belonging to the third category

In our previous paper, we had presented a novel numerical model to study the effect of the carious lesion on the strain distribution within the tooth structure (4). The current findings should be drawn and recruited in the context of any discussion about the biomechanics related to the endodontics. Living dentine had a fascinating repair of any microscopic damage by stiffening of the needed location via sensing of the odontoblast and subsequent repair. Stiffening is done via

- Addition of secondary and tertiary dentine
- Laying down intracanalicular dentine on the internal surfaces of the dentinal tubules

The dentine in the beginning will be in a soft status and gradually become stiffer with aging. The dentine structure and the fibrous nature of the dentine in its arrangement necessitating special attention to this feature. We have these criteria that in any consideration of biomechanics related to the endodontically treated teeth

- The presence of the pup inside plays an important role in determining the mechanical response of the loads and permit the distribution of the loads in the best that provide the transmission of the load in the best way that the dentine could resist
- We could consider that the dentine as a perforated material that further fine tune the total mechanical response of the dentine frame
- The shape of the teeth allows a specific harmony with the bone type whether we are speaking about the maxilla or mandible where the maxilla had softer bone than that present in the mandible
- Any part of the dentine that is deprived from its cellular milieu will be converted form modifiable material to engineering material
- Parametric approach and models partition should be considered in any numerical model

The using of the post after endodontic treatment could be necessary due to mechanical issues. Post with lower stiffness, namely lower modulus of elasticity will give distinctive pattern of bending. Dentine fatigue is a subject with scarce coverage (5). This issue needs numerical model that represent the fatigue feature to prepare a robust framework as an introduction for physical laboratory studies (6)

Methods

A generic tooth model had been used to represent the endodontically treated tooth as well as to represent the natural tooth. This model had been used in all the papers in our series about biomechanics in endodontics (7).

Figure 1 This is simple representation of the model. The PD space had been represented as it had a crucial role in determining the tooth subdomain stability

Simplification, Partitioning and segregation in the biomechanics are needed by simplification of the complicated model via representing each element of the design in a single separated model

Property	Value	Units
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Mechanical properties Elasticity modulus Poisson's ratio Density Ultimate tensile stress Tensile yield stress Compressive yield stress Default failure criterion Thermal expansion coefficient ▼ Thermal properties Thermal conductivity Specific heat capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.0000000000e+07 4.0000000000e-01 7.8500000000e+03 6.5000000000e+08 4.2500000000e+08 4.2500000000e+08 Von Mises Stress ▼ 1.2200000000e-05 4.6600000000e+01 0.0000000000e+00 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [pa] [dimensionless] [kg/m^3] [pa] [pa] [pa] [1/(degree C)] [W/(m*K)] [J/(kg*K)]

Figure 2 This is the mechanical properties of the PD ligament component

Property	Value	Units
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Mechanical properties Elasticity modulus Poisson's ratio Density Ultimate tensile stress Tensile yield stress Compressive yield stress Default failure criterion Thermal expansion coefficient ▼ Thermal properties Thermal conductivity Specific heat capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.6000000000e+11 2.0000000000e-01 1.2900000000e+03 4.0000000000e+07 3.0000000000e+07 3.0000000000e+07 Not Specified ▼ 4.1900000000e-05 2.5000000000e-01 0.0000000000e+00 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [pa] [dimensionless] [kg/m^3] [pa] [pa] [pa] [1/(degree C)] [W/(m*K)] [J/(kg*K)]

Figure 3 This is the mechanical properties of the force application holder and the stiff post in the case of the post that represent the metallic post

Property	Value	Units
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Mechanical properties Elasticity modulus Poisson's ratio Density Ultimate tensile stress Tensile yield stress Compressive yield stress Default failure criterion Thermal expansion coefficient <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Thermal properties Thermal conductivity Specific heat capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.0000000000e+09 3.0000000000e-01 7.8500000000e+03 6.5000000000e+08 4.2500000000e+08 4.2500000000e+08 Von Mises Stress ▼ 1.2200000000e-05 4.6600000000e+01 0.0000000000e+00 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [pa] [dimensionless] [kg/m³] [pa] [pa] [pa] [1/(degree C)] [W/(m*K)] [J/(kg*K)]

Figure 4 This is the mechanical properties of the bone sub-model and the soft post in the case of representing the plastic post

Property	Value	Units
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Mechanical properties Elasticity modulus Poisson's ratio Density Ultimate tensile stress Tensile yield stress Compressive yield stress Default failure criterion Thermal expansion coefficient <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Fatigue properties <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Stress-life (SN) curve Curve definition method Stress definition Fatigue strength coefficient (SRI1) First fatigue strength exponent (b1) Cycle limit of endurance/transition point (NC1) Standard error <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ Thermal properties Thermal conductivity Specific heat capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.0000000000e+09 3.0000000000e-01 7.8500000000e+03 6.5000000000e+08 4.2500000000e+08 4.2500000000e+08 Von Mises Stress ▼ 1.2200000000e-05 Review Estimate from UTS ▼ Amplitude ▼ 1.3854750000e+09 -1.2500000000e-01 1.0000000000e+06 0.0000000000e+00 4.6600000000e+01 0.0000000000e+00 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [pa] [dimensionless] [kg/m³] [pa] [pa] [pa] [1/(degree C)] [1/(degree C)] [W/(m*K)] [J/(kg*K)]

Figure 5 The dentine had been represented as linear material and with limited fatigue

Figure 6 This is the used S-N curve for the material used to represent the dentine sub-domain

We have represented a model of the effect of the caries on the prediction of the pulp response previously and the results indicate apparent strain disturbance. It is totally an ignorance when we consider unacceptable explanations such as dryness of the dentine after endodontic treatment to explain the higher rate of the roots fracture that is being faced in many cases

Figure 7 The base that is fixed is apparent and the force application site is also apparent

Results and discussions

Figure 8 This is the model with soft post

Figure 9 This is the model with stiffer post with crown made from fatigue limited material

Figure 10 Fatigue life with fiber post only

Figure 11 Fatigue life with soft post and the crown is remained

Figure 12 This is the model with stiffer post with zirconia crown and zirconia post

Figure 13 This is the model with stiffer post with crown made from fatigue limited material

Figure 14 Fatigue life with stiffer post

Figure 15 Fatigue life with stiffer post and crown

Figure 16 This is the natural tooth model which hollowed and involve the crown

Figure 17 Fatigue life with natural tooth

In the results with the more reddish region that is associated with model with the soft post, it is clearly shown the anticipated lower fatigue life (8). The numerical simulations utilizing state of art engineering tool namely finite element analysis, shows the superiority of this modality in predicting fatigue in the dental models (9)

The effect of the post is not involving the root only, but the crown portion as will. The effect on the strain distribution is extending to the bone as well as the tooth itself which will be studied in a separate paper. Different material combination will produce different pattern of stress and strains. The fatigue is associated highly with the model where softer post is used at a region where most of the failure in the dentine had high probability to start and propagate at (10).

Conclusion

We had presented numerical model which represent the feature of limited fatigue life of the material which had crucial effect of the tooth survivability as well as effect on the selection of the used material in the treatment.

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in may researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He

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